

THE RESIDUAL COMPRESSION STRENGTH OF STITCHED AND UNSTITCHED PLAIN-WEAVE CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATES AFTER IMPACT AND HYGROTHERMAL CYCLING

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SUMMARY: Damage effects due to hygrothermal cycling were experimentally studied for thin (~1mm) Carbon /Epoxy laminates containing various levels of impact damage. T300/GY260 laminates were made by Resin Transfer Moulding from plain woven fabric with various densities of through-the-thickness stitching using Kevlar threads. The cycling was conducted, on impacted and non-impacted wet specimens, over a temperature range from -30°C to +100°C with ambient humidity ranging from low to 99%. Stitching did not significantly affect the damage resistance of the laminates, nor their residual compressive strength after impact (CAI strength). The cycled specimens were only slightly more resistant to damage than the dry specimens and the saturated specimens showed further slight improvement. Hygrothermal cycling slightly decreased the CAI strength and decreased the undamaged strength.

INTRODUCTION

The use of post-buckling design in composites has raised interest in the performance of stitched thin-skinned composites. Through-the-thickness stitching is a simple technique and can be combined with liquid moulding techniques such as Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) to potentially produce low cost and high quality components with improved resistance to delamination [1, 2].

Tada and Ishikawa [3] evaluated the effects of stitching on compression strength of holed carbon fibre laminates in which Kevlar 49 threads were stitched around the hole. They found that stitching could prevent crack initiation and/or propagation at initial failure stage but had little effect on compression strength. Herszberg et. al [4] showed that Kevlar transverse stitching did not affect the residual compression strength of thin woven fabric laminates. While stitching was generally reported to improve Mode I fracture toughness [5, 6], Ogo [5] found that stitching had negligible effect on Mode II delamination toughness, while Jain and Mai [7] reported a significant increase due to stitching.

Hygrothermal cycling is a significant factor in the long term performance of polymer matrix composites for aircraft structures. Under hygrothermal cycling, interlaminar and intralaminar cracking may occur within composite structures. In particular, impact damage may spread as a result of hygrothermal cycling due to the freeze-thaw or boiling cycle of any moisture absorbed in the damaged region [8, 9]. This could affect their impact resistance and tolerance. Most work done on hygrothermal effects to date has concentrated on laminates made from unidirectional prepreg tape. Hygrothermal cycling 100 times between -54°C and 93°C caused no significant microstructural cracking of a quasi-isotropic T300/5208 laminate as detected by optical microscopy [10]. Brandt [11] reported that moisture absorbed in 24-ply T300/914C laminates did not affect significantly their residual compressive strength after impact. Birger [12] concluded that the ageing of carbon/epoxy composites at 50 and 95% relative humidity (RH) for 960 hours, although resulting in a drop in their glass transition temperature, hardly affected the mechanical properties of the material. However, other studies showed that thermal spiking to 135°C of wet XAS/914C laminates caused matrix cracking and affected the rate of subsequent moisture uptake [13, 14]. Previous results [15] showed that extensive intralaminar cracking surrounding the impacted-induced damage area due to hygrothermal cycling did not affect the residual compression strength of tape laminates.

Very few studies examined the effect of hygrothermal cycling on textile composites. Furrow and Loos [16] studied the hygrothermal effect on AS4/3501-6 stitched uniweave laminates. They found that after 160 cycles the static compression strength of the Kevlar 29 stitched uniweave laminate was reduced by nearly 10% ($-55\sim 60^{\circ}\text{C}$ with varying degree of RH). When exposed to 60°C and 95% RH for 80 days and then saturated in 70°C water, the material lost 19% of their baseline compression strength. Mitrovic and Carman [17] studied the influence of tensile fatigue damage on residual compression strength of 8 harness satin woven composites. Their results showed that residual compression strength of the material was significantly influenced by the amount of damage induced during tension-tension fatigue.

This paper reports the combined effects of hygrothermal cycling and low velocity impact (up to 6 J) on the impact resistance and residual compressive strength of thin carbon/epoxy laminates made from plain-weave fabric stitched with different stitching densities.

SPECIMEN MANUFACTURE

The test specimens, produced from Ciba Composites G1051 plain weave fabric, comprising 3K T300 tows, had a layup sequence of $[0_2,45]_s$. They were then stitched with Kevlar 49 (40 Tex) and then impregnated with Ciba Composites GY260 epoxy resin HY917/DY070 by RTM. They are cured at 80°C for 4 hours and postcured at 160°C for 4 hours. Their cured thickness was 1.1 ± 0.05 mm. Three stitch densities of 0, 4 and 8 stitches/ cm^2 were employed. The unstitched, low density stitched and high-density stitched panels were respectively designated PW, LDST, HDST. Figure 1 shows the stitch configuration.

The test specimens, of dimension 91 x 117 mm, were cut from the panel so that their long dimension was in the 0° (warp) direction. The specimens were C-scanned to ensure general quality and they were examined by optical microscope to check for any microcracking.

Fig. 1: Configuration of stitched woven fabric laminate

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Four groups of specimens were tested, each with a different sequence of impact and hygrothermal cycling. Each group comprised a number of specimens from each stitch configuration, i.e., PW, LDST and HDST. The specimens from the various designations were damaged by impacting at energy levels ranging from 0 to 6 J. Before testing all specimens were dried in an oven at 70°C until constant weight was reached. The edges of the test specimens were not sealed during conditioning since minor local edge effects would not affect the impact performance. The testing sequence for each group is outlined below and summarised in Table 1 which also includes moisture content in the non-impacted specimens and their measured glass transition temperature (T_g).

- Group A specimens were impacted at different energy levels, then compression tested.
- Group B specimens were immersed in water at 70°C until their weight reached an equilibrium (constant conditioning), then impacted at different energy levels and subsequently compression tested.
- Group C specimens were immersed in water for constant conditioning. Impact test were then performed before 810 standard hygrothermal cycles (SHC). After that some of them were subjected to constant conditioning for moisture reabsorption. The others were subsequently compression tested.
- Group D specimens were subjected to 810 standard hygrothermal cycles after constant conditioning, then impact and subsequently compression tested.

Table 1: Test matrix

Group	Test sequence	Number of specimens	Moisture content*(%)		T_g (°C)	
			at Impact	at CAI	At Impact	at CAI
A	Dry→Imp→CAI	PW: 13 LDST: 33 HDST: 17	<0.2	<0.2	146	146
B	Wet→Imp→CAI	PW: 4 LDST: 4 HDST: 4	0.62	0.62	125	125
C	Wet→Imp→SHC→CAI	PW: 6 LDST: 9 HDST: 7	0.62	0.52	125	114
D	Wet→SHC→Imp→CAI	PW: 4 LDST: 4 HDST: 5	0.52	0.52	114	114

*for non-impacted specimens

Standard Hygrothermal Cycle – SHC

The temperature ranges was -30°C to +100°C (measured at the specimen surface) with relative humidity ranging from low to 99% RH. The average heating rate was 1.1°C/min. The temperature range chosen is based on the general temperature profile for a commercial aircraft (see Ref. [18] for more detail).

Moisture Absorption and Glass Transition Temperature

Moisture absorption behaviour before and after cycling was determined by using water immersion at 70°C. Selected specimens were redried and their moisture reabsorption characteristics determined. Details on measuring weight, and determination of the effect of absorbed moisture on T_g of composite materials using dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) have been reported previously by Qi et al. [18].

Impact and CAI tests

Impact test were conducted at six different incident impact energy levels from 0 to 6 J. Compression after impact tests were conducted at room temperature using the CRC-ACS test rig. The specimen was constrained by anti-buckling plates which contained a circular cut-out of diameter 40 mm to allow any damage growth and local buckling within this window. Details of those testing and test procedures have been reported by Qi et al. [19].

Damage Characterisation

Tetrabromoethene enhanced X-ray radiography was employed to characterise the initiation and growth of microcracking (after SHC) and damage (after impact and CAI). Through transmission C-Scan was also used to determine the projected impact damage area. Optical microscopy was employed to study surface damage and failure mode and SEM was also used to investigate the fracture morphology.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Plain Woven Fabric Structures

Cross-sections of a plain-weave specimen revealed tow waviness, due to the weave structure, such that fibre tows were at out-of-plane angles of up to 8.2°. Stitching cause further out of plane crimping of the tows and also local in-plane distortion of the yarns such that diamond shaped resin-rich areas were formed in the vicinity of each stitch. No distortion of the stitch loops was found due to RTM consolidation process. This fibre/tow waviness is a major factor affecting in-plane mechanical properties of this type of laminate, especially for their undamaged compression strength [1, 4]. Dow [1] has shown that stitched flat laminates have compression strength about 20% lower than the strength of comparable unstitched laminates which may be attributed to crimping and fibre displacement and damage due to stitching.

Hygrothermal Effect

A variety of damage modes were manifest for the various specimens subsequent to cycling. These have been previously reported by Qi et al [18]. Short transverse matrix cracks and surface debonding between resin and tow fibres were observed. These microcracks grew along fibres in the tows and they were arrested in the interlacing zone of warp and weft tows. Some delamination was found in the interlacing tows of the surface plies. Figure 2 is an X-ray radiograph and shows some small dark zones at the interlace points on the surface ply. Cross-sectional microscopic inspection revealed that these were delamination cracks occurring between surface warp tows and weft tows. Stitched specimens developed cracks in the resin rich areas associated with the stitching and there was evidence of debonding at the stitch

interface. However, they were far less susceptible to the surface ply delamination cracks, as may be seen from Figure 3. This may be because the hygrothermal stresses had been relieved by the cracking in the stitch region.

Fig. 2: Matrix cracking of PW specimen, shown by short dark lines and delamination in the interlacing area (SHC; X-ray)

Fig. 3: Matrix cracking and stitch thread debonding of a HDST specimen (SHC; X-ray)

Impact Resistance

The impact damage resistance, as measured by the decrease in damage area due to impact, is shown in Fig. 4 for dry, cycled and wet PW specimens. Those data points are best fitted to linear lines. The damage resistance of the cycled specimens (Group D) was found to be higher than for the dry specimens (Group A) and the wet specimen (Groups B & C) even greater. It appears that constant water exposure enhanced matrix toughness, probably due to plasticisation of the matrix with moisture absorption. These results are consistent with the degree of moisture absorbed by the various specimens (Table 1). Similar results were found for the various stitched configurations and tape laminates [19].

Stitching did not significantly change the impact resistance, in terms of impact damage area, of dry, cycled or wet specimens. As an example, Fig. 5 presents the results for dry PW, LDST and HDST specimens.

Fig. 4: Impact performance of PW under different conditions

Fig. 5: Comparison of impact resistance between dry PW, LDST & HDST specimens

Impact Damage Mode

The projected impact damage area was circular for both non-stitched and stitched specimens. Fig. 6 shows a cross-section of dry PW specimen impacted at 4.5 J. It is interesting to note that at the maximum impact energy, the area ratio of the damage zones, measured on the back and impacted surfaces respectively, was less than 3, whereas for tape specimens this ratio is typically greater than 10. The impact damage comprised: fibre breakage, transverse matrix cracking, and tow separation. This contrasts with the large rear ply delamination areas formed in impacted tape laminates. This more localised damage and high impact resistance for the woven composite compared to conventional tape laminates, is attributed to the wavy tow structure providing greater resistance for crack propagation.

By counting the number of stitches in the impact damage area, it was found that the effective stitch density was less than the nominal stitching density. This is obviously dependent on stitching pattern. For example, for a HDST specimen, with a nominal stitch density of 8 stitches per cm², at an impact energy level of 5J, there were only nine stitches in the failure area giving an effective stitch density of only 4 stitches per cm².

Fig. 6: Cross-section view of impacted PW specimen (Group A, impacted at 4.5J)

Damage Tolerance

Failure mode

Inspection of edges and surfaces of failed specimens after CAI revealed that significant warp tow barrelling occurred and failure mode was transverse shear cracking. Further cross-sectional inspection, see Fig. 7, showed that kinking of warp tows occurred on the crack path. Since fibre kinking is a type of fibre microbuckling, it was assessed that this preceded the final shear failure. The failure mode was similar for both stitched and unstitched specimens.

In progressive loading tests the impact induced damage area was not observed to spread (Fig. 8). This contrasts with tape laminates where the impact damage region spreads under compressive loading as a result of sublaminar buckling.

Fig. 7 Kinking bands in warp tows of a HDST specimen after CAI (Group D, impacted at 3.84 J)

Fig.8 Compression failure of an impacted HDST specimen during stepped loading (Group A, X-ray , impacted at 4.5 J)

Residual Compression Strength

As may be seen from Figs. 9-12, which show the influence of damage width on residual compression strength of the various laminates, stitching did not significantly affect residual compression strength of the woven fabric laminates. This is despite the fact that stitching reduced the undamaged compressive strength [4].

No significant difference was found in the residual compressive strength, between the uncycled Group A (dry) and Group B (wet) specimens (see eg Fig. 10), indicating that plasticisation of the matrix due to moisture absorption did not affect residual compression strength. This confirms the findings of other researchers (Guild et al. [20] and Dost et al. [21]) that resin toughness has little effect on the relationship between CAI and damage diameter.

As may be seen from Figs. 10-12, Group D (cycled then impacted) specimens had a lower residual compressive strength than that of uncycled (A and B) specimens. The CAI strength for group C (impacted then cycled) specimens was intermediate. The compressive strength for undamaged cycled specimens was also lower than for the uncycled specimens. This may be because of the placement of load-bearing (0°) plies on the surface. The degradation of the matrix at the surface due to hygrothermal cycling would reduce the support to the warp tows resulting in a lower compression strength.

It was expected that the impact damage area in the Group C (impacted then cycled) specimens would grow due to cycling as a result of the freeze-thaw effect of moisture trapped in the damage area. No such damage growth was observed and the CAI strength of the Group C specimens was in fact higher than that of the Group D (cycled then impacted) specimens. This may be because for group C specimens, the impact-induced crack tips were blunted by the hygrothermal cycling.

Fig. 9 CAI strength of Influence of dry PW, LDST and HDST specimens

Fig. 10 Influence of damage induced by hydrothermal cycling on CAI strength for cycled and non-cycled PW specimens

Fig. 11 Influence of damage induced by hydrothermal cycling on CAI strength for cycled and non-cycled LDST specimens (Group A, B C and D)

Fig. 12 Influence of damage induced hydrothermal cycling on CAI strength for cycled and non-cycled HDST specimens (Group A, C and D)

Stitching Effect

In the present study, it was found that stitching did not affect significantly the residual compressive strength. This has been attributed to the fact that, as reported above, both stiched and unstiched specimens exhibited similar failure modes. The nestling of adjacent plies in the RTM fabric composite was sufficient to inhibit the sublaminar buckling which is manifest in the failure of prepreg tape laminates. The failure mode for the fabric specimens was kink band formation followed by transverse shear cracking. Such failure was not greatly influenced by stitching.

Failure analysis showed the failure projected area, as schematically shown in Fig. 13 and summarised in Table 2, was similar for PW, LDST and HDST specimens. This was

confirmed by X-ray radiography and visual inspection on the failed specimens. Table 2 showed that for LDST specimens almost no stitches were involved in the failure process, since cracks propagated between two stitching rows, while only 4 stitches per cm² were involved in the failure region for HDST specimens.

Fig. 13: A sketch showing damage propagation, the projected failure area and transverse shear crack on the edge for PW, LDST and HDST specimens

Table 2: Estimated failed stitch density during CAI

Nominal stitching density (st/cm ²)	Estimated projected failure area (cm ²)	Estimated number of stitches failed	Estimated effective stitch density (st/c m ²)
0	2 x (2d x W')	0	0
4	2 x (2d x W')	0	0
8	2 x (2d x W')	2 x (1 + W'/d)	4.1

Components of shear force would be expected to act on the through-the-thickness stitches because of the shear type failure mode. The shear properties of Kevlar/epoxy is poor compared to that of carbon/epoxy [22]. SEM photographs of a broken stitch thread, showing evidence of shear and pull-out failure, are presented in Figs. 14 and 15.

An important factor in the failure mechanism was the friction caused by the relative movement between two fractured surfaces during the transverse shear cracking. Friction may be a potential energy dissipation mechanism during mode II fracture [7]. The contribution of the stitches to resist such crack propagation was much lower than the neighbouring carbon fibres because of their small volume fraction and lower shear properties.

Fig. 14 Breakage of a stitch thread in a HDST specimen after CAI (Group D, SEM)

Fig. 15 Breakage of a stitch thread in a failed HDST specimen after CAI (SEM)

CONCLUSIONS

For the thin carbon/epoxy specimens studied, which were stitched with kevlar thread and subject to the combined effect of hygrothermal cycling and impact damage, the following conclusions were reached:

- Stitching did not increase their damage resistance or improve the residual compressive strength.
- Hygrothermal cycling caused a reduction in undamaged compressive strength and the CAI strength of both stitched and unstitched specimens. The reduction manifest in cycled then impacted specimen was greater than for impacted and cycled specimens.

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